

Impact Of Lamingo Dam On The Socio-Economic Activities Of The People In Jos Area Of Plateau State, Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the socio-economic impact of Lamingo dam on the residents of Jos area close to the dam. Primary data was collected from households residing in the area. 102 copies of well-structured questionnaires were administered to the households. Questions were related to the socio-demographic characteristics of respondents and benefits or otherwise they derive from the presence of the dam. Questions regarding the type of socio-economic activities that have sprang up as result of the presence of the dam. Data collected were analyzed using tables. The study result revealed that the presence of the dam in the study area impacted negatively on some of the socio-economic parameters such as health and land value, thus making the inhabitants of the area blame the dam for some water borne related diseases within the study area. The positive impact of the refinery on the study area is the increase in income generating ventures, commercial activities, domestic and industrial water supply. These have contributed to better livelihood for many of the inhabitants of the area. Suggestions were made towards improving the socio-economic conditions of residents.

Keywords: Socio-economic activities, Lamingo Dam, Residents, Farming, Fishing, Impact

INTRODUCTION

A dam is an artificial barrier usually constructed across a stream channel to facilitate water storage. Timber, concrete, earth, steel or a combination of these materials may be used to build the dam. Dam must have a spillway system to convey normal and excess water flows, a dam should also have drainage or other water withdrawal faculty for control pool or lake level and to lower or drain the lake under normal maintenance and emergency purpose.

In other words, dams are massive barriers built across rivers to confine and utilize the flow of water for human purpose such as agricultural, recreation, industrial and domestic water supply. Power generation (hydroelectricity) Adams (2000) added that dam maybe constructed for control of flooding and erosion as well as enhancement of recreation and tourism.

The construction of dam and a reservoir is considered as the most effective means of solving human problems of water storage in sub-humid and arid region as Bohlen & Lewis, (2008) asserted in the savanna area. Recently there are appreciable numbers of large and small dams that are constructed in different parts of Nigeria. There are socio-economic consequences in area where they are being constructed.

These schemes bring about some negative and positive socio-economic effects like farming activities , fishing activities, swimming, boat riding, training of students from different schools, car washing, block industries, increase health hazard especially those associated with water as well as psychological shock due to physical displacement and relocation of the affected population. The quality of life and convenience largely depends on the domestic water supply, increase in hygienic condition in the area would reduce the risk of water borne disease.

The most important thing which this study seeks to find out is the impact of the dam on the socio- economic condition of the people in the study area.

The study is aimed at examining the impacts of Lamingo dam on the socio-economic conditions of the people of Jos area on which can be done by: identifying the various human activities taking place within the dam area and assessing the socio-economic significance of the dam to the people within the area.

THE STUDY AREA

Jos, a city in the middle belt of Nigeria, is located on lat.9^o56'N and long.8^o53'E. It is situated almost at the geographical center of Nigeria and about 179 km (111 miles) from Abuja the nation's capital. It is linked by road, rail and air to the rest of the country. It is the administrative capital of Plateau State. The city is located on the Jos Plateau at an elevation of

about 1,238 meters/4,062 feet high above sea level. Jos the headquarters of Plateau State is bounded by Kaduna state to the north and northwest and Bauchi to the east (NPC, 2006).

For effective and clear comprehensive background of geographical area especially on the socio-economic impacts, Lamingo dam is an earth dam meant for urban water supply. It is within the hydrological zone of north central region of Nigeria. There are major tributaries that supply water to Lamingo dam which are collectively known as "RAFIN SANYE". Lamingo dam was constructed in 1973 and was constructed by Plateau State government. The dam has a height of 15.72m and a length of 3.62km with a storage capacity of 90,000m³ per day, Lamingo dam supplies 15.5% of the water supplied to Jos area. There was no case of resettlement as the dam was built on vacant land.

SOURCE: BUREAU FOR LAND, SURVEY AND TOWN PLANNING, JOS, PLATEAU STATE.

Figure 1: Map of Plateau State showing Jos North Local Government Area

Figure 2: Aerial Photograph of the Dam

MAP OF LAMINGO DAM

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The research is survey research with primary data collected from field observation of the selected areas, oral interviews and discussion with respondents, on the socio-economic impacts of Lamingo dam on the people while secondary data was gathered from non-governmental organizations, government agencies and internet, to help acquire materials such as: maps of the study area as well as existing records, pictures and documents. This data would be obtained from previous publications, published and unpublished materials, textbooks, student's dissertations, maps, internets and journals among others.

The study used the purposive sampling technique based on availability of person on site. This technique is considered to be the most convenient and appreciate method. This is because the technique is flexible in terms of respondents of selection and ensures wider coverage of the area of study when compared with other forms of technique. The inventory of all the selected areas was taken; these include the type of activities available, factors that influence the dam such as location of houses and the characteristics of the population in the dam site/area. A total of one hundred and twenty (120) people will be sampled from this study area. Sample to include sex, age and socio-economic profiles (education, work/activity, income). The questionnaire administered and collected from the wards surrounding Lamingo dam which consists Katon Rikkos, kyan Rikkos, Kampanin Goshi, Awarko, Atsi Izang, Signal Barracks, Furaka, Haske, Kwanga A and B, Zarazon, Vwang, Lamingo, Rikkos central, Zed-Bedin. Out of the 120 questionnaires that were administer only 102 copies of the questionnaires were returned.

The data collected for study is tabulated and converted into frequencies and percentages for easy comparison and easy understanding. The data generated which is aimed at establishing the degree and nature of relationship that exist between the research variables (dependent and independent).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The responses are shown in tabular form indicating or showing the number, percentages and charts of a particular option selected by the respondents, responses of the questionnaires are hereby reproduced and presented as follows:

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Sex		
Male	54	52.9
Female	48	47.1
Total	102	100.0
Age		
0-20	14	13.7
21-30	52	50.9
31-40	25	24.5
41 and Above	11	10.7
Total	102	99.8
Occupation		

Public Servant	20	19.6
Private Sector Workers	18	17.6
Self Employed	42	41.1
None	22	21.5
Total	102	99.8
Religion		
Christainity	90	88.2
Islam	05	4.9
Traditional	05	4.9
None	02	1.96
Total	102	99.96
Literacy Level		
Primary	04	3.9
Secondary	38	37.3
Tertiary	40	39.2
None	20	19.6
Total	102	100

Source: Field Survey 2014

The Table above shows that male were 54 in number representing 52.9% of the total number while female were 48 representing 47.1%, this is due to the fact that more male were easily accessible at the time of administering of the questionnaire, the table reveals that age 0-20 is 14 in number which represent 13.7% of the total percentage, from ages 21-30 are 52 in number representing 50.9% of the total percentage, 31-40 are 25 in number representing 24.5% of the total percentage and finally ages 41 and above are 11 in number representing 10.7% of the total percentage. It can be understood from the table that ages 21-30 represents a large population used in the research work. These are as a result of them being youths and are willing to express themselves and answer questions.

As regards the occupation of respondents, Public servant represents 20 respondents which is 19.6% of the total percentage, 18 were private sector workers which represents 17.6% of the total percentage, 42 respondents were self-employed which represents 41.1% of the total percentage and others which consist of mostly students were 22 represented 21.5% of the total percentage. The occupational group with the highest number of respondents as observed here are those that are self-employed. This is because most of the people in the study area have one business or the other doing to sustain their family e.g. Hair dressing salon, Block industries, Fashion designing, irrigational farming, fishing amongst others.

Religion of the respondents showed Christianity represents 90 respondents which is 88.2%, 5 respondents are Muslim which is 4.9% of the total number, 5 represent Traditional which is 4.9% and 2 represents other religions of 1.96% the total sum by percent. The study area is occupied mostly by Christians.

The table also showed the literacy levels of respondents ranging from primary school which has its total frequency of 4 representing 3.9%, the secondary school represents 38 number which has its percentage of 37.8% while that of tertiary is

40 representing 39.2% and none which has its total number of 20 representing 19.6% of the total percentage. The above data revealed that those in tertiary level and secondary school are the ones that answered majority of the questionnaire which the two sum up together make up 76.5% of the total percentage, it is always the situation in urban areas, and the secondary and tertiary level of education is usually the majority.

TABLE 2: Distance of Residence from Lamingo Dam

Distance (Km)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
2-4	36	35.3
5-7	44	43.1
8-10	18	17.6
10 and Above	04	3.9
Total	102	99.9

Source: Field Survey 2014

From the table 2 above 35% of respondents cover 2-4km from their residence to the dam. 43% covers 5-7km, 18% and 4% covers 8-10km and more than 10km respectively. The table revealed that most of the surrounding residence is closer to the dam which gave them more advantage to utilize the dam

TABLE 3: Period of stay

Period of stay (Years)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Less than a year	10	9.8
1-5	35	34.3
6-10	12	11.8
10 and Above	45	44.1
Total	102	100

Source: Field Survey 2014

The table above showed the number of years that the respondents have lived in their residence, ranging from less than a year which has the total number of 10 respondents representing 9.8% of the total percentage for 1-5years with 35 respondents representing 34.3% of the total percentage, for 6-10years which has a frequency of 12 representing 11.8% of total percentages and the highest which is for more than 10years which has a total frequency of 44.1% of the total percentage.

The information showed that most of the respondents have lived in the study area for more than 5years, which sums up percentage of 90.2% of the total percentage of 100%.

TABLE 4 Improved Livelihood as a result of Lamingo Dam

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	82	80.4
No	20	19.6
Total	102	100%

Source: Field Survey 2014

Table 4 showed that 80.4% of the respondents says their lives has increased as a result of Lamingo dam while 19.6% of the respondents says their lives has not increased as a result of Lamingo dam from the difference in the percentage. It showed that the construction of Lamingo dam has improved the living standard of the people of the study area.

TABLE 5: Socio-Economic activities at Lamingo Dam.

Activities	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Block MoldingIndustry	36	35.0

Fishing	21	20.5
Irrigation	19	18.6
Swimming	10	9.8
Mechanic Workshop	04	3.9
Nomadic Farming	07	6.8
Recreational	05	4.9
Total	102	99.5

Source: Field Survey 2014

Results from the questionnaire administered, the socio-economic activities taking place in the study area are activities like block molding industry, fishing, irrigation, swimming, mechanic workshop, nomadic farming and recreational activities. Industrial activities is the highest socio-economic activity taking place in the study area accounting for 35%, then fishing which accounts for 20.5% of the total percentage and irrigation which account 18.6% of the total percentage, swimming accounts for 9.8%, mechanic workshop accounts for 3.9%, nomadic farming accounts for 6.8% and recreational activities accounts for 4.9%.

The results of this study concurs with the findings of Mudzengi (2012) who carried out a similar study titled “An Assessment of the Socio-Economic Impacts of the Construction of Siya Dam in the Mazungunye area: Bikita District of Zimbabwe” the study revealed that Siya Dam has both positive and negative socio-economic impacts in the Mazungunye area.

However, there is need to enhance the beneficial impacts and minimize the adverse impacts of the dam.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Dams play prominent roles in the life of a society. The ultimate contribution is that it brings about development in man’s life in terms of water supply, industrialization, increasing of agricultural productivity, and employment generation for majority of citizens.

Impoundment of water in dams is among the effective and efficient way of flood control, many dams have contributed immensely to the development of some areas example Sokoto Rima River Basin Development Authority (SRRBDA).

This paper has examined the impact of the socio-economic activities of the people of Jos area on Lamingo dam. Some of the catchment areas are far away from the dam but yet about 70% of the populous sample lived in close proximity to the dam.

Some of the activities found around the dam are industries, irrigation farming, mechanic workshop, car wash, swimming, fishing, and these activities .It can thus be concluded from the above manifestation that the impact of the activities of Jos area on Lamingo dam and some of the advantages includes;

- i. Provision of portable water for drinking and other uses
 - ii. Creation of employment opportunity
 - iii. Boost in economic development e.t.c
 - iv. Generation of power supply
- The disadvantages also include:
- a. Contamination of water
 - b. Death of people as a result of swimming
 - c. Health hazard, prevalence of diseases for example, typhoid.
 - d. Causes flood

Based on the research findings, the following recommendations are offered.

The research project conducted shows that the number of youths found in study area which falls between ages 21-40 accounts for 75.4% of the total percentage dominates the study area and with this there is a possibility of more socio-economic activities to take place in the area which might affect the dam.

Dam construction is associated with many problems, ranging from positive to negative effects. All these problems could be corrected by enacting laws and regulations governing the activities around the dam which could help to discourage farmers and people with industries around the dam from polluting the dam. There should be creation of proper awareness on the effect of such activities on the dam and also open more water channels to reduce the amount of water periodically, there should also be proper sanitation on the dam. Water should be properly treated before being distributed.

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